

High-resolution observations of ^{12}CO and $^{13}\text{CO } J = 3 \rightarrow 2$ towards the NGC 6334 extended filament

I. Emission morphology and velocity structure

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ABSTRACT

NGC 6334 is a giant molecular cloud (GMC) complex that exhibits elongated filamentary structure and harbours numerous OB-stars, H II regions, and star-forming clumps. To study the emission morphology and velocity structure of the gas in the extended NGC 6334 region using high-resolution molecular line data, we made observations of the ^{12}CO and $^{13}\text{CO } J = 3 \rightarrow 2$ lines with the LAsMA instrument at the APEX telescope. The LAsMA data provided a spatial resolution of $20''$ (~ 0.16 pc) and sensitivity of 0.4 K at a spectral resolution of 0.25 km s⁻¹. Our observations revealed that gas in the extended NGC 6334 region exhibits connected velocity coherent structure over ~ 80 pc parallel to the Galactic plane. The NGC 6334 complex has its main velocity component at ~ -3.9 km s⁻¹ with two connected velocity structures at velocities ~ -9.2 km s⁻¹ (the ‘bridge’ features) and ~ -20 km s⁻¹ (the northern filament, NGC 6334-NF). We observed local velocity fluctuations at smaller spatial scales along the filament that are likely tracing local density enhancement and infall, while the broader V-shaped velocity fluctuations observed towards the NGC 6334 central ridge and G352.1 region located in the eastern filament EF1 indicate globally collapsing gas onto the filament. We investigated the ^{13}CO emission and velocity structure around 42 WISE H II regions located in the extended NGC 6334 region and found that most H II regions show signs of molecular gas dispersal from the centre (36 of 42) and intensity enhancement at their outer radii (34 of 42). Furthermore most H II regions (26 of 42) are associated with least one ATLASGAL clump within or just outside of their radii, the formation of which may have been triggered by H II bubble expansion. Typically towards larger H II regions we found visually clear signatures of bubble shells emanating from the filamentary structure. Overall the NGC 6334 filamentary complex exhibits sequential star formation from west to east. Located in the west, the GM-24 region exhibits bubbles within bubbles and is at a relatively evolved stage of star formation. The NGC 6334 central ridge is undergoing global gas infall and exhibits two gas bridge features possibly connected to the cloud-cloud collision scenario of the NGC 6334-NF and the NGC 6334 main gas component. The relatively quiescent eastern filament (EF1 - G352.1) is a hub-filament in formation, which shows the kinematic signature of global gas infall onto the filament. Our observations highlight the important role of H II regions in shaping the molecular gas emission and velocity structure as well as the overall evolution of the molecular filaments in the NGC 6334 complex.

Key words. stars: formation – ISM: structure – ISM: clouds – ISM: kinematics and dynamics – ISM: HII regions – submillimeter:ISM

Supplementary online only materials: Appendices

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References

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Appendix A: rms noise and Gaussian components: ^{13}CO (3-2)Fig. A.2: Number of Gauss components per pixel fitted to the ^{13}CO line profile toward the NGC 6334 region.

Appendix B: PV maps toward selected regions and FIR sources in the NGC 6334 central filament

Fig. B.1: Position velocity maps (bottom panels) toward three selected slices (L1 and L2 indicated in top panel) perpendicular to the central filament and toward FIR-sources (I[N], I to V indicated by red plus markers in top panel) along y-axis (latitude). Magenta circles indicate H II regions from [Anderson et al. 2014](#). The slices L1 and L2 show same regions, MFS cold and MFS warm, presented in Figure 12 of [Arzoumanian et al. 2022](#).

Appendix C: Channel maps of selected regions

Fig. C.1: Channel map of ^{13}CO and ^{12}CO toward NGC 6334 central filament region. The vertical dotted line indicates the longitude where we observe the V shape in the lv plot (in Fig ??). Magenta/red circles indicate H II regions from Anderson et al. (2014). Blue lines indicate along which the pv -maps are shown in Fig. B.1.

Fig. C.2: Channel map of ^{13}CO and ^{12}CO toward GM-24 region. Magenta/red circles indicate H II regions from [Anderson et al. \(2014\)](#).

Fig. C.3: Channel map of ^{13}CO and ^{12}CO toward G352.1 region. The vertical dotted line indicates the longitude where we observe the V shape in the lv plot. Magenta circles indicate H II regions from Anderson et al. (2014). Red star symbols show the location of ATLASGAL clumps found in the filament.

Appendix D: ^{13}CO emission maps of H II regions

Fig. D.1: ^{13}CO emission maps of H II regions integrated over -15 to $+5$ km s^{-1} , otherwise indicated inside each maps. Color wedges indicate TdV in K km s^{-1} . Cyan triangles indicate positions of the ATLASGAL clumps.

Fig. D.2: Same as Figure D.1

Appendix E: Radial profiles and contrast parameter

Fig. E.1: Azimuthally averaged ^{13}CO emission profiles (shown in green color) toward H II regions exhibiting increasing radial intensity profiles, with or without the shell/ring like features, computed from velocity range -15 to $+5$ km s^{-1} . Vertical black line indicate the radii from Anderson et al. 2014 and vertical green line indicate sizes estimated from ^{13}CO emission profiles. Horizontal black line indicates 50% value of the intensity maxima.

Fig. E.2: Same as Fig. E.1.

Fig. E.3: Same as Fig. E.1 for H II regions exhibiting centrally peaked emission with decreasing intensity profiles or flat radial profiles. In addition, magenta radial line profiles are shown for particular velocity ranges labelled at the bottom left corner of each plots.

Fig. E.4: Contrast values of 1000 randomly sampled shells/rings obtained from ^{13}CO moment map for velocity ranges -15 to $+5$ km s^{-1} and radii $0.6R$ to $1.2R$, where R is radius of randomly selected region. The radius of randomly created rings range from $20''$ to $700''$, similar to the sizes of H II regions found in NGC 6334 extended region. 1σ range of contrast values are indicated by the dotted red lines.

Appendix F: Longitude-velocity (lv) and latitude-velocity (bv) plots

Fig. F.1: Longitude-velocity (lv) and latitude-velocity (bv) plots toward the H II sources. Color bars shows Gaussian peak intensity (T_A^* [K]). Ellipse in red color (if present) indicate visual fit to the velocity structure to infer expansion velocities. Red lines are used to indicate tentative V-shapes in the velocity structure. Name of the H II regions are given on top of each pair of maps.

Fig. F.2: Same as Figure F.1

Fig. F.3: Same as Figure F.1

Fig. F.4: Same as Figure F.1

Fig. F.5: Same as Figure F.1

Table F.1: Expansion velocities of the H II regions derived from an elliptical fit to the lv or bv plots. Fit parameters (central position in $[l,v]$ or $[b,v]$, diameter in x-axis [deg], diameter in y-axis [km/s] and position angle [deg]) are given in Col.2. Derived expansion velocities V_{exp} in km/s are given in Col. 3.

H II region	Fit parameters ($x, y, D1, D2, \theta$)	V_{exp} [km s^{-1}]
G350.240+00.654	0.655, -7.5, 0.372, 10, -65	5.0
G350.401+01.037	1.037, -7.5, 0.207, 8, -40	4.0
G350.482+0.952	0.952, -10, 0.053, 8, 10	4.0
G350.505+0.957	0.957, -10, 0.053, 8, 10	4.0
G350.675+0.832	350.675, -5, 0.060, 7, 5	3.5
G350.71+0.642	0.642, -8, 0.408, 10., 40	5.0
G351.367+0.641	0.641, -5.5, 0.059, 8, 5	4.0
G351.42+0.638	0.638, -5, 0.029, 12, 5	4.0
G351.462+0.557	0.557, -2.5, 0.038, 8, 10	4.0
G351.766+0.493	0.493, -4, 0.120, 9, -20.	4.5
G351.835+0.757	351.835, -3.5, 0.048, 8, -5	4.0
G352.171+0.307	0.307, -6, 0.235, 10, -40	5.0

Fig. F.6: Top: ^{13}CO moment0 map. H II regions that show signature of V-shaped velocity structure in Fig F.1 to F.5 are shown in red circles. Blue lines from L3 to L12 indicate the slices in which PV maps are constructed with widths of three beam size (0.016 deg). Bottom panels: PV maps along the blue lines indicated in the top panel image. Observed V-shaped velocity structure (red lines) and velocity gradient (dotted red lines) are indicated in each maps.

Fig. F.7: ^{13}CO moment one map toward G352 region (EF1). The velocity gradient in hub-filament candidate EF1 filament is clearly observable.